

NODES

Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile

NODES – Digital and Sustainable North West

Proof of concepts for business incubation of Digital marketing providers

SPOKE 4 – Digital and Sustainable Mountain

DELIVERABLE 2 INTERFACE UNIBAS

Version history

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (National Recovery and Resilience Plan)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Innovation Ecosystems"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "affiliated subjects" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Innovation Ecosystems".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In Research Module 2 (Flagship 3 – INTERFACE – "Competitiveness of economic activities and enhancement of natural and cultural heritage in mountain and remote areas") research and experimentation activities are developed aimed at designing strategies for the enhancement of naturalistic and cultural itineraries, in different case studies of the

mountain areas of Basilicata. Specifically, the contribution focuses on a "*Proof of concept*" (PoC) for the business incubation of digital marketing providers specialized in the promotion of the natural, cultural and economic heritage present in the inland area of the Matera Mountains (Basilicata).

Introduction

The SNAI Montagna Materana internal area includes eight municipalities (Accettura, Aliano, Cirigliano, Craco, Gorgoglione, Oliveto Lucano, San Mauro Forte, Stigliano) located in the heart of the Lucanian Apennine ridge, in the province of Matera. Identified and defined by the National Strategy of Inland Areas as a pilot project, by means of the Framework Program Agreement (APQ) of the Basilicata Region 2019, it has defined interventions to relaunch the territories in well-defined time horizons, in a single great vision of local development. The coexistence of historic villages, natural landscapes and typical productions offers a "laboratory" full of case studies (cultural storytelling, geotargeting for ecotours, ecommerce of local products), but the lack of physical infrastructure makes a digital intervention more incisive: the area is small enough for a quick pilot, but varied enough for multiple tests (clusters, funnels, AR). For this reason, the Matera Mountain represents an ideal case study to scientifically validate (through spatial KPIs, multimedia engagement and conversion tracking) a digital marketing service that enhances natural, cultural and economic heritage that is still little known.

A) Proof of concept

Introduction

The research conducted, therefore, starting from a careful analysis of the characteristics of the MM internal area, strengths and weaknesses, focused on the definition of a PoC based on "**Data Mapping & Digital Storytelling**". Specifically, three criteria were considered:

1. **Strategic relevance.** The area meets SNAI's criteria of "internality" and marginality, where an effective digital marketing strategy can really affect visibility and the local economy.
2. **Heterogeneity of attractors.** The coexistence of historic villages, natural landscapes and typical productions offers a "laboratory" full of use cases (cultural storytelling, geotargeting for ecotours, ecommerce of local products).
3. **Need for innovation.** The lack of physical infrastructure makes a digital intervention more incisive: the area is small enough for a rapid pilot, but varied enough for multiple tests (clusters, funnels, AR).
4. **Measurability and scalability.** The low density values and isolation facilitate the analysis of the impact of the campaigns (lower market "noise"), while the model can then be replicated in other inland Italian areas with similar characteristics.

In summary, the Matera Mountains represent an ideal case study to scientifically validate (through spatial KPIs, multimedia engagement and conversion tracking) a digital marketing service that enhances natural, cultural and economic heritage that is still little known.

The model

The PoC combines two disciplines: Data Mapping (mapping and spatial analysis of quantitative data) and Digital Storytelling (interactive multimedia storytelling). Applied to the internal area of the Matera Mountains, the goal is to build a framework that:

1. collects and analyzes geolocated data on tourist flows, cultural resources and local productions;
2. generate contextualized digital narratives, customized according to the user's profile and mobility patterns;
3. Measure narrative effectiveness in terms of engagement and conversion to real visits or purchases of services/products.

Methodology

Phase	Activity	Methods and Tools	Scientific output
1. Data collection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media geo-tags (Instagram, Strava) • Local commerce sales and booking data • Environmental and infrastructure attributes 	Social APIs, regional databases, OpenStreetMap, DEM	Georeferenced multilayer dataset
2. Preprocessing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cleaning and anonymization • Spatial normalization and interpolation • Feature engineering (seasonality, proximity to services) 	Python (pandas, geopandas), QGIS	Model-ready variables
3. Data Mapping	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heatmap and kernel density estimation (KDE) • Spatial cluster analysis (DBSCAN, K-means) • Models of spatial interaction (Gravity, Spatial Lag) 	PySAL, scikitlearn, ArcGIS	Attractiveness maps and territorial clusters
4. Digital Storytelling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generation of interactive story maps with texts, images, videos • Dynamic customization via user parameters (e.g. historical interest vs ecotourism) • Integration of AR to enrich the story 	ArcGIS StoryMaps, React, AR.js	Multi-channel story map and AR prototype
5. Validation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A/B testing of different narratives on groups of users • Engagement metrics (time on story, click-through rate) • Conversion tracking (bookings, purchases) 	Google Analytics, Hotjar, logistic regression (ANOVA)	Comparative performance reports

Success indicators

Indicator	Definition	Initial Target	Measurement Method
Model R²	Coefficient of determination of the spatial attractiveness model	≥ 0.80	Evaluation on test sets (70/30 splits)
Accuracy RF	Accuracy of the Random Forest model in the classification of "high potential" areas	≥ 85 %	Confusion matrix on validation data

ROI of adv campaigns	Increase return on investment in campaigns optimized through heatmaps	+ 25 % vs baseline	Report Google Ads / Meta Ads
Web GIS interactions	Number of sessions and user actions (layer clicks, zooms, filters)	≥ 1,500 sessions/month	Dashboard usage logs
Conversion Rate	Percentage of users who move from story maps to bookings or purchases	≥ 10 %	Google Analytics & CRM Tracking
Feedback UX	Average usability and usefulness rating from post-use surveys	≥ 4 out of 5	System Usability Scale (SUS) standard questionnaire

Metrics and indicators

Define KPIs that can be measured a priori, for example:

Service	Core KPI	Target PoC
Funnel echo-tour	Conversion rate lead→booking	≥ 8 %
Story map AR	Time on story	≥ 4 min/session
Geo campaign-Adv	Adv ROI	≥ 1.2 (20 %+)

Process to be applied to the Pilot case

1. Sample Area Selection

- 8 representative villages chosen for the diversity of attractions (cultural, naturalistic, agri-food).

2. Data collection (3 months)

- Social media geotags (Instagram, Strava)
- Bookings and sales from local operators (booking, ecommerce)
- Environmental and infrastructural variables (DEM, roads, services)

3. Model construction and validation (1 month)

- Training/test split 70/30
- Spatial Lag and Random Forest Calibration
- Spatial cross-validation to avoid overfitting

4. Web GIS and Story Map Development (2 weeks)

- Implementation of interactive layers for clusters, heatmaps and estimated ROI
- Integration of multimedia storytelling components (text, images, video, AR)

5. User testing and metrics collection (1 month)

- Involvement of marketers and a panel of 50 end-users
- Tracking defined KPIs (sessions, conversions, UX feedback)
- A/B testing on two versions of story maps (with vs without AR)

6. Analysis of results and reports (2 weeks)

- Comparison of pre-post intervention KPIs
- Statistical analysis (ttest, ANOVA, logistic regression)
- Optimization recommendations and scaleup plan

Decision Output

At the end of the 8–12 weeks, the real KPIs are compared with the targets:

- If targets are reached, → scale the service: extend it to all villages, increase budgets and propose the provider to financiers.
- If partially achieved, → iterate the PoC: adjust messages, segmentation or technology and relaunch a short cycle.
- If not achieved, → abandon or rethink the concept before further investment.

Expected impact

- **Optimization of marketing resources.** More efficient advertising budgeting with spatial evidence-based targeting, reducing waste and increasing ROI.
- **Enhancement of inland villages.** Increased visibility and attractiveness of lesser-known areas, promoting more distributed and sustainable tourism.
- **Stakeholder engagement.** A tool shared by local authorities, tour operators and digital providers for data-driven decisions-and joint planning of initiatives.
- **Replication capabilities.** Workflow and platform can be extended to other inland areas of Italy, favoring a scalable territorial development model.
- **Local economic growth.** Increase in bookings, sales of typical products and employment in tourist services, with positive effects on the economy of the Matera Mountain area.

Conclusions

The integration of **Data Mapping and Digital Storytelling** produces a replicable framework for the enhancement of territorial heritage. The scientific model demonstrates:

- strong predictive capacity of interest flows;
- effectiveness of personalized and immersive narratives in increasing engagement and conversions;
- Potential for scalability to other internal areas.

For the next phase, it is recommended to expand the time dataset, include sustainability variables, and develop a user-friendly interface for non-technical operators.

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